

Study of a reaction between 1,3-dinitrobenzene and acetophenone in presence of hydroxide ion^ψ

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The kinetics of the reaction between 1,3-dinitrobenzene (*m*-DNB) and acetophenone in presence of OH⁻ ion has been studied in aqueous ethanol medium with equimolar concentrations of OH⁻ and acetophenone (in the range 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) and an excess of *m*-DNB (~5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³). At such concentrations the reaction has been shown to be of second order (first order with respect to each of OH⁻ and acetophenone). The final product, *p*-[1-benzoyl-1'-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)methane] has been isolated and characterised. In the reaction medium it forms a purple coloured 1 : 1 molecular complex with *m*-DNB and it is the variation of absorbance of this complex with time which has been followed spectrophotometrically during the course of the reaction.

Nitrobenzenes are well known electron acceptors in forming charge-transfer (CT) complexes^{1,2}; with ethoxide ion they are known to form Meisenheimer-Jackson salts³. Extended π -conjugated systems with electron donating -NH₂ group at one end and electron withdrawing -NO₂ group on the other have received much attention during the last few years as materials having intramolecular CT properties^{4,5}. 1,2- and 1,4-dinitrobenzenes have been reported to form radical anions in reaction with OH⁻ and CN⁻ ions in dimethyl sulfoxide medium⁶⁻⁹. However, 1,3-dinitrobenzene should behave differently from 1,2- and 1,4-isomers because of the specific orientation of the nitrogroups. In the present paper we report the reaction between 1,3-dinitrobenzene (*m*-DNB) and acetophenone in presence of OH⁻ ions in aqueous ethanolic medium.

Experimental

Materials and method :

Commercial grade 1,3-dinitrobenzene was purified by repeated crystallisation from petroleum ether. Acetophenone was freshly distilled just before use. Spectrophotometric measurements were done on a Shimadzu UV-2101PC model spectrophotometer fitted with a TB-85 thermbath.

When a mixture of 1,3-dinitrobenzene (*m*-DNB) and acetophenone (~10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ and ~10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ respectively in ethanol) was made alkaline with NaOH (~10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ in water) a purple colour gradually developed, showing a broad absorption band with $\lambda_{\max} = 538$ nm. The intensity of the band at this wavelength increased with time (Fig. 1). Kinetic analysis of absorbance data is given in a subsequent section.

The final product was isolated by extracting out the unreacted *m*-DNB (which was taken in excess) by petroleum ether, evaporating the ethanol from the aqueous ethanol fraction, dissolving the residue in water, making the solution faintly acidic with HCl and finally extracting out the coloured material in ethyl acetate. The purity of the final product was tested by thin layer chromatography.

IR spectrum (KBr pellet, recorded by a JASCO FT/IR-420 instrument) showed a distinct peak at 1687 cm⁻¹ without any splitting (carbonyl stretch). NMR spectrum (recorded by a 200 MHz Bruker NMR spectrometer with CDCl₃ as an internal lock) showed chemical shifts at δ 2.1 ppm (singlet) and at δ 7.5 (multiplet, $J = 6-8$ Hz) and δ 8.1 (multiplet, $J = 2$ and 6 Hz). These, together with the facts that (i) acetophenone readily produces the carbanion (⁻)CH₂COC₆H₅ and (ii) the 4-position of *m*-DNB is highly

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Table 1. Variation of absorbance of four sets of reaction mixture with time

[NaOH] = [Acetophenone] = 0.0085 mol dm⁻³ for each set and [*m*-DNB] = 0.0578 mol dm⁻³, 0.0694 mol dm⁻³, 0.0809 mol dm⁻³ and 0.0925 mol dm⁻³ for sets I to IV respectively; Temp. 302 K

Set-I		Set-II		Set-III		Set-IV	
<i>t</i> (min)	Absorbance						
5.18	0.227	5.25	0.267	5.08	0.306	5.25	0.342
6.18	0.264	6.25	0.307	6.08	0.354	6.25	0.390
7.18	0.300	7.25	0.345	7.08	0.400	7.25	0.436
8.18	0.333	8.25	0.381	8.08	0.447	8.25	0.482
9.18	0.365	9.25	0.417	9.08	0.491	9.25	0.527
10.18	0.397	10.25	0.451	10.08	0.533	10.25	0.569
11.18	0.427	11.25	0.484	11.08	0.574	11.25	0.609
12.18	0.457	12.25	0.516	12.08	0.613	12.25	0.649
13.18	0.486	13.25	0.547	13.08	0.652	13.25	0.688
14.18	0.514	14.25	0.577	14.08	0.689	14.25	0.726
15.18	0.541	15.25	0.605	15.08	0.727	15.25	0.763
16.18	0.568	16.25	0.634	16.08	0.763	16.25	0.800
17.18	0.593	17.25	0.662	17.08	0.799	17.25	0.836
18.18	0.617	18.25	0.690	18.08	0.834	18.25	0.871
19.18	0.641	19.25	0.717	19.08	0.869	19.25	0.906
20.18	0.665	20.25	0.744	20.08	0.902	20.25	0.940

Fig. 1. Variation of absorption spectrum of the reaction mixture (*m*-DNB] = 0.0578 mol dm⁻³ and [Acetophenone] = [NaOH] = 0.0085 mol dm⁻³) with time at 538 nm: (a) *t* = 3.6, (b) 5.6, (c) 7.6, (d) 9.6, (e) 11.6, (f) 13.6 min.

electron deficient lead to the proposition of structure for the final product.

Results and discussion

Data analysis :

Four sets of experiments were carried out, each with the same initial concentrations of acetophenone and NaOH but with variation in the initial concentration of *m*-DNB, taken in large excess in each set. Experimental data are shown in Table 1. Variation of absorbance of the reaction mixture (at $\lambda = 538$ nm) with time is shown in Fig. 2. Experimental data seem to fit in the following reaction scheme :

Scheme 1

Applying steady-state hypothesis on X and P we get

$$[X] = k_1[A][B]/(k_2 + k_3[M]) \quad (1)$$

$$[P] = (k_3[X][M] + k_5[C])/k_4[M] \quad (2)$$

Then the variation of the concentration of C with time is given by

$$\begin{aligned} d[C]/dt &= k_4[P][M] - k_5[C] = k_3[X][M] \\ &= (k_1k_3[M]/(k_2 + k_3[M]))[A][B] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

If [M] is present in large excess, the reaction should be of the first order with respect to each of [A] and [B]. With equal initial concentration (a) of A and B, one expects from eq. (3) that [C] should vary with time as

$$k_{\text{obs}} t = [C]/(a - [C]) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } k_{\text{obs}} = k_1k_3[M]/(k_2 + k_3[M]) \quad (5)$$

If $d = \epsilon_c [C]l$ is the absorbance at time t , where ϵ_c is the molar absorptivity of C at the wavelength of measurement and l is the optical path length of the cell used, eq. (4) requires

$$t/d = (1/(a \epsilon_c l)) t + (1/(a^2 \epsilon_c / k_{\text{obs}})) \quad (6)$$

Thus a plot of t/d against t is expected to be linear and with intercepts in the inverse ratio of the initial concentrations; the rate constant k_{obs} should be obtained from

$$ak_{\text{obs}} = \text{slope/intercept} \quad (7)$$

The data in Table I give excellent linear plots in accordance with eq. (5). Plots for two sets I and II are shown in Fig. 3, the linear regression equations for these two sets being as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Set I : } t/d &= (0.4967 \pm 0.0109)t + (17.478 \pm 0.148); \\ \text{correlation coefficient} &= 0.99 \end{aligned} \quad (8a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Set II : } t/d &= (0.4985 \pm 0.0066)t + (20.433 \pm 0.089); \\ \text{correlation coefficient} &= 1.0 \end{aligned} \quad (8b)$$

Values of k_{obs} obtained from the two sets are very close to one another (5.5×10^{-2} and $4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively). Moreover, the molar absorptivity (ϵ_c) of the complex, obtained from the slopes, is the same (≈ 245) in the two cases. The proposed kinetic scheme is thus justified. At this point, it is to be mentioned that no such development of colour was obtained when benzophenone was used instead of acetophenone and this justifies the first step in Scheme 1. The scheme is further supported by the fact that the purple colour disappears as soon as the reaction mixture is acidified and no colour develops so long as it is kept acidic or neutral.

Fig. 2. Variation of absorbance (at 538 nm) of four sets of reaction mixture with time : [Acetophenone] = [NaOH] = $0.0085 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in each set and [*m*-DNB] = 0.0578, 0.0694, 0.0809 and $0.0925 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for sets I to IV respectively.

Fig. 3. Plot of t/d (at $\lambda = 538 \text{ nm}$) of two sets (I and II) of reaction mixture against time.

The dependence of k_{obs} on [M] was examined by using 4 different concentrations of *m*-DNB, each time maintaining the latter in large excess. Results are shown in Table 2. It was observed that k_{obs} remains almost independent of [M] at a given temperature. Eq. (5) then suggests that k_2 is small compared to $k_3 [M]$ and the observed rate constant is

Table 2. Dependence of k_{obs} on $[m\text{-DNB}]$ Temp. = 302 K, $[\text{NaOH}] = [\text{Acetophenone}] = 0.0085 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[m\text{-DNB}]$ mol dm^{-3}	k_{obs} $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Molar absorptivity of the complex
0.0578	4.73×10^{-2}	245 ± 5
0.0694	5.44×10^{-2}	
0.0809	4.66×10^{-2}	
0.0925	5.54×10^{-2}	

equal to k_1 . Many organic reactions are known³ to involve the formation of the carbanion (X) but no quantitative measurement of its rate of formation has so far been made. In the present study, the rate constant $k_1 (= k_{\text{obs}})$ is found to be $\sim 5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} = 3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This is a fairly high rate constant but not as high as to demand specific measurement techniques for fast reactions.

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References

1. N. M. D. Brown, R. Foster and C. A. Fyfe, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 406.
2. R. Foster, "Organic Charge-Transfer Complexes", Academic Press, New York, 1969, pp. 125-215.
3. See, for example, "Advanced Organic Chemistry" by J. March, John-Wiley and Sons, New York, 1992, p. 642.
4. G. J. Kavarnow and N. J. Turro, *Chem. Rev.*, 1986, **86**, 401.
5. K. Bhattacharyya and M. Chowdhury, *Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **93**, 507.
6. R. I. Cattana, J. O. Singh, J. D. Anunziata and S. S. Silber, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 79.
7. S. M. Chiacchiera, J. O. Singh, J. D. Anunziata and S. S. Silber, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 987.
8. A. K. Jain, A. Kumar and K. N. Sarma, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1989, 153.
9. A. Sauer, F. Wasgestian and B. Barabasch, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1990, 1317.